

ISic1244

I.Sicily inscription 1244

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary (?)

Material

marble

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Messina

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140729

1. [— —]πιδος Σα[ρ]α [πί]ωνος (?)
2. τοῦ Ἐπιάνακτος.
- 3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492847

EDCS 39101609

PHI 140729

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae*

Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0417 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)
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